

Effects of purine bases and nucleosides on the survival of cortical rat astrocytes *in vitro*

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ABSTRACT

Purines are responsible for the regulation of many physiological and pathological processes in the central nervous system including the development and remodeling of tissues after trauma, stress, ischemia, and neurodegenerative diseases. The extracellular concentration of purines significantly increases under conditions of stress. We investigated the effects of purine nucleosides and nucleobases on primary cultures of Wistar rat astrocytes not only under physiological conditions, but also after deprivation of energy depots by using iodoacetic acid, and assessed whether the investigated molecules exhibited cytoprotective or cytotoxic effects. An MTT test was used to evaluate cell viability, whereas flow cytometry analysis was employed to evaluate the presence of free oxygen species. Survival of astrocytes (as evidenced by the MTT test) decreased on treatment with 500 μM iodoacetic acid for 40 min (to 58.4% compared with untreated controls). The cytotoxic effect of iodoacetic acid was partially reversed by co-treatment with either 200 μM adenosine (to 80.3% of control) or 200 μM guanosine (to 83.3% of control), whereas the application of inosine or adenine had no effect. Iodoacetic acid alone did not increase the production of free oxygen radicals, but the induction of oxidative stress was observed

during the concurrent incubation of astrocytes with 200 μM adenosine and 500 μM iodoacetic acid. We conclude that, under energy deprivation, adenosine and guanosine stimulate the survival of astrocytes by means of the recovery of intracellular ATP.

KEYWORDS: astrocytes, purines, cell viability, MTT, iodoacetate

INTRODUCTION

The normal functioning of the central nervous system (CNS) is the result of the balanced interaction of neurons and their complex relationships with glial cells. Astrocytes have a highly important role in maintaining the homeostasis of the CNS, mainly by regulating the transport of ions and neurotransmitters. Thereby, astrocytes are involved in the development of neurons and the modulation of synaptic transmission [1]. Astrocytes are also one of the most active participants in processes initiated by brain injury, ischemia, and inflammation. Purine nucleotides such as adenosine-5'-triphosphate (ATP) and guanosine-5'-triphosphate (GTP), their nucleosides adenosine and guanosine, and the nucleobases adenine, guanine, and inosine are highly important intercellular signaling molecules. In the nervous system, they play a role as neurotransmitters and neuromodulators and provide trophic support and energetic substrates, which, in turn, induce changes in cellular metabolism, structure, and function. Extracellular purines stimulate the synthesis and release of growth factors from

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astrocytes, including bFGF (basic fibroblast growth factor), NGF (nerve growth factor), neurotrophin-3, and S100 β protein [2]. Purine nucleosides and nucleotides, especially guanosine, ATP, and GTP, stimulate mitosis *in vitro* as evidenced by the increased incorporation of thymidine into DNA of astrocytes and microglia. On the other hand, the presence of adenosine at high concentrations can potentially induce apoptosis [3]. Numerous data are available regarding the participation of adenosine in the regulation of sleep behavior and in the “plastic” changes involved in memory and learning processes [4]. Certainly, the two basic functions of adenosine in the CNS are neuromodulation and neuroprotection. All these effects are achieved by the activation of surface purinergic receptors [5] or by other mechanisms initiated after purine uptake into target cells [6]. Purines play an important role in the pathophysiology of numerous acute and chronic disorders in CNS, and astrocytes are the main source of cerebral purines [7]. Indeed, under physiological conditions, a corresponding constitutive concentration of purines exists. However, situations of stress (brain injury, ischemia, trauma, inflammation, and neurodegenerative diseases) lead to their significant increase [8]. Adenosine arises in the extracellular space of the brain in two major ways. The first involves the decomposition of adenine nucleotides to 5'-AMP by exonucleotidase and exophosphodiesterase and then further to adenosine by 5'-nucleotidase [9]. The second involves the efflux of adenosine from cells by using adenosine nucleoside transporter proteins [10]. Moreover, large quantities of the purine nucleosides guanosine and inosine can be released into the extracellular fluid of the brain during ischemia. In addition, extracellular GTP increases the release of adenine nucleotides, whereas guanosine stimulates the release of adenosine and its metabolic products, the most important being inosine. The extracellularly accumulated purine molecules might be eliminated through the blood-brain barrier [11] or taken up by astrocytes via transport proteins.

Our aim has been to clarify the effects of purine nucleosides and nucleobases on astrocytes not only under physiological conditions, but also in terms of the energy deprivation of depots, and to assess whether the investigated molecules exhibit cytoprotective or cytotoxic effects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Unless otherwise indicated, all laboratory chemicals were obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland) or Invitrogen (Darmstadt, Germany). All materials used in the tissue cultures were purchased from Nunc (Roskilde, Denmark) and Sarstedt (Karlsruhe, Germany).

Preparation of primary cultures of rat astrocytes

Male rats of the Wistar strain, aged 7 days, were used. They were housed in our animal colony according to standard conditions and following current guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals. After decapitation, the brain cortex was quickly removed and homogenized by mechanical disruption in 2 ml modified RPMI medium (1% glutamine and gentamicin antibiotic, 0.1% pyruvate, 5 mM glucose, 2 mM glutamine, and 10% fetal calf serum (FCS)). The obtained homogenate was centrifuged at 1400 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was discarded, and the resultant cell suspension was diluted in modified RPMI medium, transferred to poly L-lysine-covered cell culture flasks, and incubated for 24 h in a humidified 95% air/5% CO₂ atmosphere at 37°C. After 24 h (and thereafter at appropriate time intervals), medium was replaced with new modified RPMI medium. Passaging of cells was performed after the cells had reached confluence during the appropriate time intervals. For the experiment, astrocytes were grown on 96-well plates (for viability testing; initial concentration, 50000 cells/well) or 12-well plates (for flow cytometry analysis; initial concentration ~700000 cells/well). After 15 days of culture (90% confluence), medium was replaced with modified RPMI medium containing the purines of interest. Purine concentrations and the duration of incubation are indicated in the results section.

Testing the viability of astrocytes by MTT

Mitochondrial activity is considered a parameter of cell viability and is commonly assessed with the MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) method, which is based on the reduction of yellow water-soluble MTT by active mitochondria to an insoluble blue formazan. After the appropriate treatment with

purines, cells were rinsed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to remove dead non-adherent cells, and the cells were then incubated in modified RPMI medium containing MTT (0.5 mg/ml medium) at 37°C for 35 minutes. An appropriate volume (50 μ l) of solubilization solution dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) is added to dissolve the insoluble purple formazan product into a colored solution. Extinction was measured at 570 nm with an Eppendorf Biophotometer.

Detection of free radicals by dihydrorhodamine and flow cytometry

Dihydrorhodamine (DHR) color is used to detect oxidative stress. The method is based on the oxidation of DHR 123 to rhodamine 123 in the presence of free radicals. Rhodamine 123 has an intense green fluorescence that can be measured by various fluorescence detection techniques. Cells were incubated during purine treatment with DHR 123 (final concentration, 1 μ M). Upon the completion of incubation, cells were trypsinized with modified RPMI containing 0.25% trypsin/0.02% EDTA solution, washed twice in PBS, and resuspended in 0.5 ml PBS. Resuspended cells were subjected to an analysis of fluorescence by a FACS scan (Becton Dickinson, San Jose, USA) at 530 nm. The analysis was performed by CellQuest software (Becton Dickinson, Mountain View, CA, USA).

Statistical analysis of results

Viability data are presented as means $\pm$ SD. All values were obtained from three repeated experiments. The viability of treated cells is presented, compared with the viability of control (untreated cells, viability 100%). Unless specified otherwise, a two-tailed unpaired Student's *t* test or an analysis of variance with Dunnett's pairwise comparison was performed to assess the statistical significance of results. Statistical significance was accepted when $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Effect of adenosine, guanosine, inosine, and adenine on the survival of astrocytes in culture

The results of the effects of various concentrations of adenosine (from pathological to physiological) on astrocytes in the culture (incubation time

Figure 1. Effects of various concentrations of adenosine on astrocyte viability. Astrocyte viability is presented as a percentage (%) of viable cells compared with control (100%). All values are presented as means $\pm$ SD and were obtained from three independent experiments.

60 min) are shown graphically (Figure 1). Compared with the control (untreated astrocytes, viability 100%), none of the tested concentrations of adenosine (5 μ M to 500 μ M) led to a significant change in the viability of astrocytes ($P > 0.05$ compared with control). The same procedure was repeated with guanosine and inosine and with the purine base adenine, and similar results were obtained, i.e., no significant change was seen in cell viability ($P > 0.05$ compared with control; data not shown).

Time kinetics of iodacetate action

From the literature, we know that IAA at a concentration of 0.5 mM can be used in experiments for the inhibition of glycolysis [12]. The dependence of the viability of astrocytes on the exposure time with 0.5 mM IAA is shown graphically (Figure 2). The viability of astrocytes decreased with increasing length of exposure to 0.5 mM IAA. Because the viability of astrocytes was significantly decreased to $49.4 \pm 8.0\%$ compared with the control after 40 min incubation; duration of 40 min was used for all IAA incubations in the following experiments.

Effect of purine nucleosides and bases during inhibition of glycolysis

The effect of purine nucleosides and nucleobases under conditions of chemically simulated ischemia

Figure 2. Action of iodoacetic acid (concentration 0.5 mM) in primary culture of astrocytes. Astrocyte viability is presented as a percentage (%) of viable cells compared with control (100% viability). All values are presented as means $\pm$ SD and were obtained from three independent experiments.

*Asterisks represent a statistically significant difference compared with the control ($P < 0.05$)

was assessed by the concurrent treatment of astrocytes with appropriate concentrations of nucleoside/nucleobase (12, 25, 50, 100, and 200 μ M) and 0.5 mM of IAA for 40 min. The concurrent treatment with the nucleosides adenosine or guanosine at concentrations of 200 μ M showed a protective effect on astrocyte viability during the subsequent inhibition of glycolysis with 0.5 mM IAA ($P < 0.05$; Figure 3). The survival of astrocytes increased from $56.4 \pm 3.0\%$ (treatment with 0.5 mM IAA) to $84.0 \pm 9.2\%$ in the presence of 200 μ M adenosine and to $88.2 \pm 5.2\%$ in the presence of 200 μ M guanosine. However, the presence of inosine and adenine did not lead to a statistically significant improvement of viability compared to the treatment with IAA alone ($P > 0.05$).

Analysis of reactive oxygen species during application of adenosine and IAA

In order to examine the involvement of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the cell damage induced by IAA and to investigate the effect of concurrent adenosine treatment, cells were treated as in the previous experiment and subsequently analyzed by DHR 123 treatment and flow cytometry for the

Figure 3. Effect of the purine nucleosides adenosine, guanosine, and inosine and the adenine base on astrocytes when glycolysis is concurrently inhibited by iodoacetic acid (0.5 mM). Astrocyte viability is presented as a percentage (%) of viable cells compared with control incubation without IAA and purines (100%). All values are presented as means $\pm$ SD and were obtained from three independent experiments.

*Asterisks represent a statistically significant difference compared with 0.5 mM IAA ($P < 0.05$).

presence of free oxygen radicals. The results are presented in the form of FACS histograms (Figure 4). The presence of 0.5 mM IAA compared with no-treatment (control) did not lead to changes in the geometric average mean, which is considered as relevant statistical value. An increasing geometric mean value would correspond to the histogram being shifted to the right as the result of an increased production of free radicals, and thus a detectable increase in the intensity of fluorescence (geometric means were 5.23 for the control and 5.72 in the presence of 0.5 mM IAA; $P > 0.05$). However, a concurrent treatment with adenosine (200 μ M for 60 min) in the presence of IAA (0.5 mM) led to an increase in the geometric mean (to 11.73, $P < 0.05$), indicating an increase in fluorescence intensity, i.e., an increased production of free oxygen radicals. At other concentrations of adenosine (12 μ M, 25 μ M, 50 μ M, and 100 μ M), no statistically significant changes were observed ($P > 0.05$), data are not shown.

Figure 4. FACS analysis of the presence of ROS (reactive oxygen species) during application of adenosine and iodoacetic acid (IAA) in astrocytes. Histogram displays changes in fluorescence of dihydrorhodamine (DHR) under various cell treatments: Control (A), 0.5 mM IAA (B), adenosine 200 μ M (C), and simultaneous treatment with adenosine 200 μ M and 0.5 mM IAA (D).

DISCUSSION

In the present study, we have applied the technique of the primary culture of rat astrocytes *in vitro* to assess the effect of various purines on astrocyte survival. Extracellular purine concentrations

increase in stressful and energy-limited conditions in the brain. The purines can be removed from brain through the blood-brain and blood-liquor barriers; however, the uptake of purines into astrocyte cells and into cells of the brain parenchyma is the dominant pathway for their removal (especially of adenosine) [13]. The activation of A₃ receptors and the modulation of the enzyme activity of SAH (S-adenosylhomocystein hydrolase) have been proposed as a mechanism to promote the adenosine-mediated activation of apoptosis under these conditions [14]. Therefore, we have investigated the effects of various concentrations of adenosine, guanosine, inosine, and adenine on astrocyte survival in the present study. In contrast to the expectations derived from literature, none of the tested molecules and concentrations (from 5 to 500 μ M) affects the viability of astrocytes. The results have led us to test the possibility that these molecules (at concentrations of 12 μ M to 200 μ M) have a protective effect on astrocytes under conditions of chemically simulated ischemia induced by iodoacetate, a glucose-6-phosphate-dehydrogenase inhibitor. The inhibition of glycolysis is known to decrease the intracellular concentration of ATP, which compromises cell viability. We have observed that the purine nucleosides, adenosine, and guanosine, when applied at concentrations of 200 μ M, exhibit a protective effect on astrocytes with reduced ATP content, whereas this effect is absent during the application of inosine and adenine. The protective action of adenosine is likely via metabolic action and not via adenosine receptor signaling. Adenosine as a hydrophilic molecule can rapidly enter the cell by its corresponding nucleoside transporter. The adenosine is then phosphorylated by adenosine kinase, and such a molecule can easily be used to replenish the intracellular ATP depot. This mechanism potentially underlies the protective effect of adenosine on astrocytes under conditions of ischemia [15]. Confirmation of this assumption is reinforced by the finding that inosine, a metabolite of intracellular adenosine and potent agonist at several adenosine receptors [16], shows no protective effect. This might also indicate that the adenosine kinase reaction is increased under conditions of ATP deprivation at the expense of adenosine deaminase. Thus, the phosphorylation

of adenosine to AMP and further to ATP might explain the acute restoration and preservation of the intracellular ATP pool, thereby preserving the integrity and viability of cells. Unlike adenosine (and inosine), guanosine does not act at classical purine receptors. However, it exerts similar effects on astrocytes, apparently by increasing the GTP pool, which in turn has favorable effect on ATP and energy homeostasis [17]. Many cells, including astrocytes, produce H₂O₂ and ROS, especially during the reperfusion of ischemic areas [18]. Hydrogen peroxide and ROS might directly damage cellular structures, which may be enforced by reduced intracellular ATP, NADPH and glutathione contents, i.e., by a reduced antioxidant potential of cells. The application of DHR 123 and flow cytometry analysis in the presence of IAA have not lead to the detection of any increased production of free radicals, which implies that the viability reduction of astrocytes in the presence of 0.5 mM IAA (40-min incubation) cannot be explained by the induction of oxidative stress. However, an increased production of free oxygen radicals occurs during the incubation of astrocytes with adenosine (200 μM, as a pre-treatment) and iodacetate (0.5 mM), i.e., hydrogen peroxide is released during the catabolism of adenosine. This can be explained by the increased oxidative stress caused by incubation with the highest concentration of adenosine, which corresponds to a pathologically extreme value of increased extracellular adenosine. The source of ROS during reperfusion of ischemic organs is often xanthine oxidase, which generates hydrogen peroxide. The increased intensity of intracellular metabolism of adenosine under conditions of chemical ischemia (induced by IAA) might be attributable to the cells having to take up adenosine to a greater extent to restore their depot ATP. This also indicates that adenosine (200 μM) under energy-limiting conditions (provided by the action of IAA) has the ability to reconstruct intracellular ATP. The latter mechanism may explain cytoprotection even in the presence of concurrently increased oxidative stress and allows for improved survival of astrocytes *in vitro*. The nucleosides adenosine and guanosine thus act protectively on astrocytes under conditions of intracellular ATP depletion caused by the inhibition

of glycolysis. This knowledge provides the basis for new research to examine the specific mechanisms by which these nucleosides exert their effect on energy and cytoprotective effects under limiting conditions such as cerebral ischemia.

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